

ISic3195

I.Sicily inscription 3195

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Vigna Cassia

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI329592

1. Πάεις.

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645525

PHI 329592

Bibliography

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Orsi, P. 1923. Manipulus epigraphicus christianus memoriae aeternae I.B. de

Rossi dicatus. Contributi alla Siracusa sotterranea. *Atti della Pontificia Accademia Romana di Archeologia. Memorie*. 1: 113-122. At no.24

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